

BCOMING

D2.4 Validated Multiplex Serological Assays

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Executive Summary

BCOMING is a multidisciplinary project with partners and teams collecting samples from all terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, from humans and animals, in Cambodia, Ivory Coast, Guinea and Guadeloupe. It is therefore very important to standardize sampling collection and subsequent laboratory analysis. This deliverable concerns the serological analysis of filoviruses and coronaviruses to test for the presence of antibodies in humans and wildlife.

In this deliverable, the final versions of the SOPs are attached. The assays for ebolavirus have been updated and now include Marburg virus, another zoonotic filovirus with potential cross-reactivity with ebolaviruses.

Additionally, an assay has been developed to test antibodies against Lassavirus and is included in this deliverable.

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Multiplex serological assays

Multiplex assay to test antibodies against Ebolaviruses and Marburg

For the serological analysis of Ebolaviruses, a multiplex assay has been adapted and optimized based on the initial version of the assay published by Ayouba and colleagues¹ (1). The current version includes 10 recombinant proteins representing different viral regions (nucleoprotein [NP], 40-kDa viral protein [VP40], and glycoprotein [GP]) from five of the six Ebolavirus species: Zaire Ebolavirus (EBOV); Sudanvirus (SUDV); Bundibugyo (BDBV); Reston (RESTV), Bombali virus (BOMV) and Marburgvirus (MARV). The test is standardized to analyse samples collected as plasma, serum or dried blood spots from humans, bats and rodents. Standard operating procedures (SOPs) are available in English to be shared with all participating laboratories in BCOMING.

Multiplex assay to test antibodies against Coronaviruses

Similarly, for the serological analysis of Coronaviruses, another multiplex assay has been adapted and optimized based on the initial version of the assay published by Ayouba and colleagues². The current version includes 20 recombinant proteins representing spike (SP) and nucleoprotein (NP) from the three beta coronaviruses that are highly pathogenic for humans (SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 and MERS-CoV), four coronaviruses that cause only mild disease (two beta coronaviruses, OC43, and HKU1; two alpha coronaviruses, 229E and NL63,) and three beta coronaviruses that circulate in bats (HKU9, nobecov subgenus isolated from Rousettus bats in China; HKU3, sarbecov subgenus isolated from Rhinolophus bats in China; 133/2005 merbecov subgenus from Tylonycteris bat in China). The test is standardized to test samples collected as plasma, serum or dried blood spots from humans, bats and rodents. SOPs are available in English to be shared with all participating laboratories in BCOMING.

Multiplex assay to test antibodies against Lassavirus

Similarly, for the serological analysis of Coronaviruses and Ebolaviruses, another multiplex assay has been adapted and optimized based on the initial version of the assay published by Ayouba and colleagues³. The current version includes 3 recombinant proteins representing capsid, nucleoprotein (NP) and Z antigen from Lassavirus. The test is standardized to test samples collected as plasma, serum or dried blood spots from humans and rodents. SOPs are available in English to be shared with all participating laboratories in BCOMING.

¹ Ayouba A, Touré A, Butel C, Keita AK, Binetruy F, Sow MS, Foulongne V, Delaporte E, Peeters M. Development of a Sensitive and Specific Serological Assay Based on Luminex Technology for Detection of Antibodies to Zaire Ebola Virus. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2016 Dec 28;55(1):165-176. doi: 10.1128/JCM.01979-16. PMID: 27795350; PMCID: PMC5228227.

² Ayouba A, Thaurignac G, Morquin D, Tuaille E, Raulino R, Nkuba A, Lacroix A, Vidal N, Foulongne V, Le Moing V, Reynes J, Delaporte E, Peeters M. Multiplex detection and dynamics of IgG antibodies to SARS-CoV2 and the highly pathogenic human coronaviruses SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. *J Clin Virol.* 2020 Aug;129:104521. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2020.104521.

³ Ayouba A, Thaurignac G, Morquin D, Tuaille E, Raulino R, Nkuba A, Lacroix A, Vidal N, Foulongne V, Le Moing V, Reynes J, Delaporte E, Peeters M. Multiplex detection and dynamics of IgG antibodies to SARS-CoV2 and the highly pathogenic human coronaviruses SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. *J Clin Virol.* 2020 Aug;129:104521. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2020.104521.

Transfer of technology and training

To facilitate knowledge transfer and implementation, the technology and training protocols for screening antibodies to Ebola, Coronaviruses and Lassaviruses have been transferred to CERFIG and the staff from CERFIG have been trained. Furthermore, the protocols for coupling of beads and antibody detection against coronaviruses have been transferred to IPC.

Annexes

Annex 1. SOP multiplex serology for Filoviruses and Marburgvirus

	Multiplex Immunoassay Luminex® filoviruses
OBJECTIVE	Instructions for carrying out the multiplex serological test using xMAP technology (Luminex®) carried out as part of the BCOMING project
STAFF INVOLVED	Technicians Researchers
DOCUMENTATION REFERENCES	<p>Development of a Sensitive and Specific Serological Assay Based on Luminex Technology for Detection of Antibodies to Zaire Ebola Virus. Ayouba A, Touré A, Butel C, Keita AK, Binetruy F, Sow MS, Foulongne V, Delaporte E, Peeters M. J Clin Microbiol. 2016 Dec 28;55(1):165-176. doi: 10.1128/JCM.01979-16. PMID: 27795350; PMCID: PMC5228227.</p> <p>The xMAP® Cookbook, 5th Edition</p> <p>Bio-Plex Amine Coupling Kit Instruction Manual</p> <p>xMAP MagPix User Manual</p> <p>Bio-Plex® 200 System Hardware Instruction Manual</p>
DEVELOPED BY	Guillaume Thaurignac Signature : Date :
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1. DEFINITIONS

Luminex®: generic term designating a luminometer allowing the demonstration of an interaction between ligands (antigen-antibody, primer-target, hormone-receptor, etc.).

BSA : Bovine Serum Albumin

PBS : Phosphate Buffered Saline

SVF : Fetal calf serum

2. PRINCIPLES

Luminex® technology works according to the combined principles of ELISA and flow cytometry through the use of fluorescent beads. The beads each have a different color to identify the antigen to which they have been coupled. It is a biotinylated secondary antibody (directed against human IgG for example) which, associated with streptavidin coupled with phycoerythrin (SAPE) makes it possible to quantify the presence or absence of interaction by an MFI value (Median Fluorescence Intensity).

3. INSTRUCTIONS AND PROCEDURES

3.1. Security Procedures

All biological material must be considered potentially infectious. Therefore, wearing gloves and lab-coat is mandatory during handling.

3.2. Materials and Equipment

The handling of Luminex beads (coupled or not), fluorochromes (PE) and certain coupling reagents are sensitive to light. A dark or light-controlled room is therefore necessary. A source of clean water is necessary whether for the preparation of buffers or for the maintenance of the machines. We have a reverse osmosis unit in our laboratory.

3.2.1. Materials

- A complete xMap system: for example MagPix or Bio-plex 200 (with Kits and consumables)
- Manual magnetic washer compatible for 96-well plates
- Vortex
- Plate shaker (required amplitude 400 - 1200 RPM) (at least 2)
- Racks compatible with tubes used (see below)
- Pipettes (P3, P10, P20, P100, P200 et P1000) and compatible filterless tips
- Multichannel pipettes 30 – 300 µL (8 and 12 channels) and compatible filterless tips
- Fridge and freezer (-20°C and -80°C) – cold room at +4°C
- Magnetic stirrer and magnetic bars
- Scales and weighing cups
- A dry water bath or heating block

- USB barcode reader (AZERTY standard)
- Bath sonicator
- Magnetic support (surebeads magnetic rack 16 tube holder, Bio-Rad)
- Wheel with support for 1.5mL tubes

3.2.2. Consumables

- 96-well flat-bottomed plates, Greiner (ref. 655906) with compatible lids
- Reusable reagent reservoirs
- 50mL, 15mL and 5mL tubes with cap (Falcon) and compatible racks
- 1.4mL tubes (micronic) with compatible racks
- Glass bottles of 0.5L, 1L and 2L
- Personal protective equipment (gloves, lab-coat)
- 1.5mL and 2mL microtubes (and compatible storage boxes)
- 1.5mL Eppendorf tubes of “Protein LoBind” quality
- Absorbent paper
- Aluminum foil

3.2.3. Reagents

- Biotinilated anti-human IgG-gamma chain specific antibody (500µg/mL) BD Pharmigen réf. 555785)
- Streptavidin-R-phycoerythrin (SAPE) (Fisher Scientific, S866)
- NaCl (powder)
- NaH₂PO₄ (powder)
- NaHPO₄ (powder)
- Magnetic COOH beads of different colors (one color per antigen), Bio-Rad/Luminex (always keep away from light!) ref. MagPlex™ MC100XX-01
- Antigens (table below)
- Isopropanol (70%)
- NaOH (0.1N)
- Bleach (diluted to 1% active Cl)
- Ethanol 70% (to clean benches) with sprayer
- Monoclonal Antibodies (LA63 (Creative Diagnostics) and KZ52 (Absolute Antibody)
- EDC (chlorhydrate de 1-éthyle-3-(3-diméthylaminopropyle)carbodiimide) (réf. Pierce : 22980)
- Sulfo-NHS (N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide)(réf. Pierce : 24510) (keep away of light! keep at -20°C)
- Amine Coupling Kit, (Bio Rad, 171406001)

3.2.4. Details on antigens used in the assay

Name	Company / Reference	Quantity for size 1 coupling (Final Vol=150µL – 6 plates) (µg)
NP EBOV	Sinobiological 40443-V07E1	2
GP EBOV Kiss	Sinobiological 40442-V08B1	2
GP EBOV May	Sinobiological 40304-V08B1	2
VP40 EBOV	Sinobiological 40446-V07E	2
NP SUDV	Sinobiological 40444-V07E	2
GP1 SUDV	Sinobiological 40094-V08B	1
VP40 SUDV	Sinobiological 40447-V07E	2
GP1 BDBV	Sinobiological 40368-V08B	2
VP40 BDBV	Sinobiological 40448-V07E	2
GP RESTV	IBT Bioservice 0504-015	2
GP1 BOMV	Sinobiological IT1-2	2
NP MARV	Cusabio CSB- EP333984LBR	2
GP1 MARV	Native Antigen REC32050	2
VP40 MARV	Cusabio CSB- EP638155LAA T	0.5

3.3. Procedure

3.3.1. Preparing the buffers

Note the name and date of preparation of each buffer.

- **Hypertonic PBS: example for 1 L of solution**

NaH₂PO₄= 0,8 g

Na₂HPO₄= 2,5 g

NaCl= 88 g

Qsp 1L d'H₂O sterile reverse osmosis-purified

Store at +4°C.

- **PBS 1X**: Put 1 tablet (tablet) in 500mL of sterile reverse osmosis-purified water
Store at +4°C.

- **Reading Buffer**: PBS 1X + 1% BSA (store at +4°C)
(approximately 200mL per plate)

- **Dilution buffer** (store at +4°C):
 - 50% hypertonic PBS
 - 1% BSA
 - 5% SVF inactivated at 56°C for 30min
 - 0.2% Tween-20
 - Qsp H₂O sterile reverse osmosis-purified(Approximately 400mL per plate)

3.3.2. Procedures and Methods

3.3.2.1. Inactivation and storage of samples

The samples to be tested with Luminex must not present any infectious risk. Before any reading, they must be inactivated according to the required health and safety rules, if possible in a BSL3 laboratory.

- If necessary, aliquot under a PSM a sufficient quantity of material. For plasmas, 50µL is generally a volume that allows several Luminex tests to be repeated.

- Inactivate for 30 minutes at 56°C in a dry water bath or 1 hour in an incubator at 56°C

After inactivation, the inactivated aliquots must be stored at -80°C or, failing that, at -20°C.

All precautions will be taken to avoid freezing-defrosting cycles as much as possible.

3.3.2.2. Coupling of antigens to beads

The procedures below allow the creation of a coupling for the production of six plates (i.e. 270 duplicate samples). Simply adjust the volumes **marked with an asterisk** proportionally for larger couplings

3.3.2.2.1. Materials and equipment specific for coupling

Materials

- Vortex
- Pipettes (P3, P10, P100-P200, P1000) and compatible filterless tips
- Magnetic rack (surebeads magnetic rack 16 tube holder)
- Wheel with support for 1.5mL tubes
- Bath sonicator

Consumables

- 1.5mL Eppendorf tubes of "Protein LoBind" quality

Reagents

- Recombinant proteins
- Magnetic COOH beads of different colors (one color per antigen), Bio-Rad/Luminex (always keep away from light!) ref. MagPlex™ MC100XX-01
- EDC (chlorhydrate de 1-éthyle-3-(3-diméthylaminopropyle)carbodiimide) (réf. Pierce : 22980) (keep away from light ! store at -20°C)
- Sulfo-NHS (N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide)(réf. Pierce : 24510) (keep away from light ! store at -20°C)
- Amine Coupling Kit, Bio Rad

3.3.2.2.2. Manipulations specific to coupling

3.3.2.2.2.1. Activation of beads and coupling

- a. Select the colors to activate; identify the tubes by the name of the recombinant protein to be coupled and the bead number
- b. Vortex the vial of beads for 30 sec, sonicate the vial for 30 sec.
- c. Add **100µl*** of beads into a 1.5mL Eppendorf tube of "Protein LoBind" quality which prevents the beads from sticking to the walls and avoids thus formation of a clear pellet. By default, use a tube provided in the coupling kit but be very careful about the dispersion of the beads and their closure system which is not hermetic (loss of beads during vortexing, evaporation during storage).
- d. Place on the magnetic holder for 1 minute.
- e. Gently remove the supernatant (with a p100);
- f. Add **100µl*** of "bead wash buffer"; Vortex for 30 sec and sonicate for 10 sec; Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute then remove the supernatant.
- g. Re-suspend the pellet in **80µl*** of "bead activation buffer"; Vortex for 30 sec and sonicate for 30 sec.
- h. Prepare immediately (or defrost the aliquots) EDC and S-NHS (protect from light, in aluminum foil or in a drawer);
- i. Keeping the vortex rotating, add **10µl*** of EDC at 50mg/ml, Vortex immediately after, then very quickly

- add **10µl*** of S-NHS at 50mg/ml.
- j. vortex again immediately.
 - k. Vortex vigorously for 30 sec, incubate under agitation (wheel), at room temperature and in the dark (aluminum foil) for 20 minutes.
 - l. After 20 min, add 150µl of PBS (provided in the coupling kit) and Vortex for 10 sec. Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute.
 - m. Eliminate the supernatant, add 500µl of PBS from the kit. Vortex for 10 sec, place on the magnetic support for 1 minute.
 - n. Gently remove the supernatant and resuspend the beads in **100µl*** of PBS from the kit. Vortex at medium speed for 30 sec and sonicate for 15 sec.
 - o. Add the **optimal quantity*** of recombinant proteins (see table in part 3.2.4) to the activated beads from the previous step and vortex 30sec.
 - p. Adjust the volume to 400 µl qsp with 1X PBS (from the kit) and vortex 10sec
 - q. Incubate for 2 hours at room temperature, under agitation and in the dark.
 - r. Place on the magnetic support for 1 min; Gently remove the supernatant with a p1000.
 - s. Wash the beads with 500 µl of PBS; Vortex for 10 sec then place on the magnetic support for 1 minute and gently remove the supernatant (p1000). Do not sonicate.

3.3.2.2.2. Saturation

- a. Re-suspend the coupled beads (steps above) in 250µl of “**blocking buffer**” (provided in the kit); Vortex at moderate speed (1000 rpm) for 15 sec.
- b. Incubate for 30 min at room temperature, with shaking (wheel) and in the dark.
- c. Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute; Gently remove the supernatant.
- d. Wash the coupled beads with 500 µl of “**Storage buffer**”, Vortex for 10 sec then place on the magnetic support for 2 minutes and gently remove the supernatant.
- e. Re-suspend the coupled beads in 150 µl* of “Storage buffer” from the Kit.

Date and store the coupled beads at +4°C, keep away from light (can be stored for at least 1 year)

3.3.2.2.3. Validation of batch of coupled beads

This validation is essential because it guarantees the effectiveness of the manipulations which will be carried out subsequently.

This validation consists by testing reference samples (usual positive and negative control panel) under the conditions of the test described in this document. The data obtained are compared to reference values obtained with previous batches of coupled beads.

The variation coefficient %CV between values need to be less than 30%.

3.3.2.3. Detection of antibodies assay for human samples

This procedure includes overnight incubation (16 hours) and therefore takes place over two days.

NB - The procedures below describe manual washes. The use of automatic washers (magnetic vacuum washes) is

possible and recommended (this reduces bias due to handlers by standardizing washes). Simply adapt the procedures below in the washer program.

3.3.2.3.1. Manipulations of the first day

3.3.2.3.1.1. Sample dilution

Dilutions are carried out in 1.4mL tubes. First of all, you must prepare a rack with as many tubes as there are samples to test. During this step, it is necessary to create the plan of the plate which will remain identical until the end of the manipulation.

For each plate, remember to include positive and negative controls which will cover as much as possible the panels of recombinant proteins used and include also a blank well (buffer only).

Their values will be used for the overall validation of the plates.

The dilution factor of samples for this assay is 1000. (1 μ l of serum or plasma in 999 μ l of dilution buffer)

The minimal volume of diluted sample needed for the assay is 125 μ l.

Dilutions can be stored for a maximum of 24 hours at 4°C.

3.3.2.3.1.2. Preparing the bead mix

Antigen-coupled Luminex beads are light sensitive. All manipulations from this stage must be done protected from light (in a dark room for example).

When coupling the antigens to the beads, bead colors were chosen for each antigen. As such, each Antigen/Bead pair must have a different color (bead number (example #18)

The quantity of coupled beads to deposit is 0.25 μ L per well, all in a final volume of 50 μ L per well, which corresponds to approximately 2000 beads per well of each color.

Consider including a margin of error in your mix. For example, for a plate (96 wells) it is appropriate to prepare a mix for 100 wells.

For 100 wells, 25 μ L of each coupled bead will need to be deposited into a final volume of 5000 μ L of dilution buffer.

To prepare the bead mix:

- Vortex the coupled beads for 30 seconds.
- Take the necessary volume from each bead
- Add in the sample dilution buffer
- Vortex everything for 30 seconds.

Wrap the tube with the mix of the coupled beads with aluminum to protect it from light.

To produce several plates simultaneously, handling should be kept to a minimum by creating a common mix (by

multiplying the volumes for a plate described above by the number of plates to be produced).

The bead mixture can be stored for a maximum of 2 hours at 4°C, protect from light.

3.3.2.3.1.3. Depositing the beads and diluted samples

First place the plate shaker at 4°C in a cold room or refrigerator).

- Identify a 96-well flat-bottom plate and its lid
- Vortex the mixture of beads for 30 seconds
- Add 50µl of bead mix /well to all wells with a multichannel pipette
- **Place the plate on the magnetic support for 45sec and remove the supernatant by inverting**
- Distribute 100µL/well of diluted samples by homogenizing (aspiration/discharge) with the multichannel pipette.
- Place the plastic cover on the plate and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Place on the shaker at 4°C.
- Set the agitator to 400rpm.
- **Incubate for at least 16 hours (overnight) at 4°C (cold room/refrigerator).**

3.3.2.3.2. Manipulations of the second day

Allow the buffers to be at room temperature.

3.3.2.3.2.1. Washing and adding the anti-IgG conjugate

A biotinylated anti-human IgG-gamma chain specific antibody (500µg/mL) is used at a final concentration of **4µg/mL** (for a final volume of 50µL of conjugate solution/well).

Example for 1 plate: you need 100 wells x 50µL of solution at 4µg/ml = 5 ml of conjugate solution at 4µg/mL final (i.e. 40µL of anti-human IgG at 500µg/mL in 4960µL of dilution buffer)

- Prepare the conjugate solution in dilution buffer
- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum foil (place the shaker at room temperature)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 1/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 2/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 3/5**)

- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 4/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 5/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, place 50µL/well of the diluted conjugate solution.
- Put the plastic cover on the plate and place the plate on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Reduce the shaker speed to **400 RPM** and incubate for **30 minutes at room temperature**.

3.3.2.3.2.2. Washing and adding Streptavidin-PE (SAPE)

Streptavidin-PE (1mg/mL) is used at a final concentration of **4µg/mL** (for a final volume of 50µL of conjugate solution/well).

Example for a plate: you need 100 wells x 50µL of solution at 4µg/ml = 5 ml of conjugate solution at 4µg/mL final (i.e. 20µL of Streptavidin-PE at 1mg/mL) in 4980µL of dilution buffer)

At the end of the incubation with the anti-IgG conjugate:

- Prepare the final Streptavidin-PE solution at **4µg/mL** in dilution buffer
- Cover the diluted Streptavidin-PE tube with aluminum foil to protect it from light.
- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 1/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 2/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 3/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 4/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 5/5**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, place 50µL/well of the Streptavidin-PE solution at 4µg/mL final concentration
- Place the plastic cover on the plate and place it on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Reduce the shaker speed to **400 RPM** and incubate for **10 minutes at room temperature**.

3.3.2.3.2.3. Washing and preparation of plate for Luminex reading

At the end of incubation with Streptavidin-PE:

- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 1/5**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 2/5**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 3/5**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 4/5**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 5/5**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well
- Place the plastic cover back on the plate and place it on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Adjust the reading buffer volume according to the Luminex platform used (the final volume is 100µL for the MagPix and 125µL for the Bioplex200) (*details available in section 3.2.2.3 1.2.2.1 Final Reading Volume depending on the automates*)

The plate can now be read by a Luminex reader (MagPix or Bioplex200).

3.3.2.4. Procedure for using and maintenance Luminex automates

Several Luminex machines can be to read plates: The Bioplex 200 in Low RP1 setting and the MagPix.

Some machines include lasers which require a preheating step (30 min). It will therefore be necessary to turn them on beforehand to be able to read the plates and carry out pre- and post-reading maintenance.

All manipulations and incidents are recorded in a notebook specific to each Luminex automates.

3.3.2.4.1. Use of Bioplex200 / LX100-200

LX100 or Bioplex200 are two designations describing the same automate supplied by different suppliers, Luminex and Bio-Rad respectively). We will subsequently only describe the maintenance conditions of the Bio-Rad Bioplex200.

3.3.2.4.1.1. Materials and Reagents specific to Bioplex200

- Reverse osmosis/distilled water
- Isopropanol 70%
- 0.1N NaOH
- Bleach (2.6° and or 9.6° Cl)
- Calibration kit (30 reactions) – Bio-Rad
- Validation kit (30 reactions) – Bio-Rad
- xMAP Sheath Fluid PLUS, 20L – Luminex

3.3.2.4.1.2. Conditions of use of the Bioplex200

In order to use Bioplex200 in this study, you must read and follow the manufacturer's recommendations. All details on the procedures described below are recorded there (available on the site luminexcorp.com).

The start-up procedure must be carried out each time the Bioplex-200 is switched on.

It is also necessary to periodically adjust the height of the probe.

The control settings must be checked by the complete validation procedure (Optic, Fluidics, Reporter and Classify) at least once a month. If one of the parameters does not fall within the validation window defined by the manufacturer, maintenance should be carried out to correct this. If this persists, contact Luminex support service.

A calibration control must be carried out daily for each use. This can be combined with the device startup procedure. This calibration is carried out each morning before reading the plates. Cleaning between each plate is recommended (Wash between plates).

It is also important to ensure the permanent presence of Sheath Fluid to supply the machine.

At the end of using the device, carry out the shutdown procedure which includes decontamination and eliminates all traces of salts, particularly at the probe level.

Often, an obstruction/contamination of the fluidics is the cause of validation and/or calibration failures. The Unclog and Sanitize procedures can remedy this in addition to a complete cleaning of the sampling probe (with osmosis water and ultrasound). Sanitize should be carried out preventively at least once a week.

3.3.2.4.2. Using the MagPix

3.3.2.4.2.1. Materials and Reagents specific to Intelliflex

- Reverse osmosis/distilled water

- Isopropanol 70%
- 0.1N NaOH
- Bleach (2.6° and or 9.6° Cl)
- Calibration kit (25 reactions) – Luminex
- Performance verification kit (25 reactions) – Luminex
- xMAP Drive Fluid PLUS – Luminex

3.3.2.4.2.2. MagPix Terms of Use

In order to use MagPix in this study, you should read and follow the manufacturer's recommendations. All details on the procedures described below are recorded there (available on the site luminexcorp.com).

It is also necessary to adjust the height of the probe weekly.

The control settings must be checked daily by the complete performance verification procedure (Optic, Fluidics, Reporter and Classify) each time it is used. If one of the parameters does not fall within the validation window defined by the manufacturer, maintenance should be carried out to correct this and if this persists, contact the Luminex support service. This is done in the morning before reading the plates.

Calibration of the MagPix must be carried out weekly.

Cleaning between each plate is recommended (Post Batch Routine).

It is also important to ensure the permanent presence of Drive Fluid to supply the machine.

At the end of using the device, carry out the shutdown procedure which includes decontamination and eliminates all traces of salts, particularly at the probe level.

Often an obstruction/contamination of the fluidics is the cause of validation and/or calibration failures. The Remove Clog and Sanitize procedures can correct this in addition to a complete cleaning of the sampling probe (with reverse osmosis water and ultrasound). Sanitize should be carried out preventively at least once a week.

3.3.2.4.3. Final reading volume depending on the automates

The final volumes to be deposited in the plates differ depending on the machines and are described in the table below:

	MagPix	Bio-Plex 200
Buffer volume for final reading	100µL	125µL
Volume to add after the last agitation during procedure or “preparation for reading”	50µL + 50µL	50µL + 75µL

3.3.2.5. Processing and validation of results – Databases

The export of results after plate varies according to the device:

- Export in Excel format from the result file for the Bioplex200
- Export the results for the MagPix in Xponent format (CSV)

The data used for further analysis are the Net MFI (raw MFI difference and Blank MFI). For Intelliflex, a preparatory step based on the raw MFI is necessary (subtraction of the blank value from the raw MFI)

4. Additional information – Condition to perform the assay with animal sample

Species	Samples Final Dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time	Congugate reference	Congugate final dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time	SAPE final dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time
Human	1/1000	4°C	overnight	Biotin Mouse anti-human IgG (BD réf. 555785)	4µg/µl	ambient	30min	4µg/µl	ambient	10min
Bat	1/2000	4°C	overnight	Goat anti-Bat IgG Heavy and Light Chain Antibody Biotinylated (BéthyI - A140-118B)	1/10000	ambient	30min	4µg/µl	ambient	10min
Rodent	1/200	4°C	overnight	Biotin goat anti-rat IgG (sigma - B7139) and Biotin goat anti-mouse IgG (JacksonR -115-065-068)	1/4000 (one mix with the two congugate)	ambient	30min	4µg/µl	ambient	10min

Annex 2. SOP multiplex serology for Coronaviruses

	Multiplex Immunoassay Luminex® Coronaviruses
OBJECTIVE	Instructions for carrying out the multiplex serological test using xMAP technology (Luminex®) carried out as part of the BCOMING project
STAFF INVOLVED	Technicians Researchers
DOCUMENTATION REFERENCES	<p>Development of a Sensitive and Specific Serological Assay Based on Luminex Technology for Detection of Antibodies to Zaire Ebola Virus. Ayouba A, Touré A, Butel C, Keita AK, Binetry F, Sow MS, Foulongne V, Delaporte E, Peeters M. J Clin Microbiol. 2016 Dec 28;55(1):165-176. doi: 10.1128/JCM.01979-16. PMID: 27795350; PMCID: PMC5228227.</p> <p>The xMAP® Cookbook, 5th Edition</p> <p>Bio-Plex Amine Coupling Kit Instruction Manual</p> <p>xMAP MagPix User Manual</p> <p>Bio-Plex® 200 System Hardware Instruction Manual</p>
DEVELOPED BY	Guillaume Thaurignac Signature : Date :
Modified by	
APPROVED BY	Martine Peeters et Ahidjo Ayouba Signature : Date :

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1. DEFINITIONS

Luminex®: generic term designating a luminometer allowing the demonstration of an interaction between ligands (antigen-antibody, primer-target, hormone-receptor, etc.).

BSA : Bovine Serum Albumin

PBS : Phosphate Buffered Saline

SVF : Fetal calf serum

2. PRINCIPLES

Luminex® technology works according to the combined principles of ELISA and flow cytometry through the use of fluorescent beads. The beads each have a different color to identify the antigen to which they have been coupled. It is a biotinylated secondary antibody (directed against human IgG for example) which, associated with streptavidin coupled with phycoerythrin (SAPE) makes it possible to quantify the presence or absence of interaction by an MFI value (Median Fluorescence Intensity).

3. INSTRUCTIONS AND PROCEDURES

3.1. Security Procedures

All biological material must be considered potentially infectious. Therefore, wearing gloves and lab-coat is mandatory during handling.

3.2. Materials and Equipment

The handling of Luminex beads (coupled or not), fluorochromes (PE) and certain coupling reagents are sensitive to light. A dark or light-controlled room is therefore necessary. A source of clean water is necessary whether for the preparation of buffers or for the maintenance of the machines. We have a reverse osmosis unit in our laboratory.

3.2.1. Materials

- A complete xMap system: for example MagPix or Bio-plex 200 (with Kits and consumables)
- Manual magnetic washer compatible for 96-well plates
- Vortex
- Plate shaker (required amplitude 400 - 1200 RPM) (at least 2)
- Racks compatible with tubes used (see below)
- Pipettes (P3, P10, P20, P100, P200 et P1000) and compatible filterless tips
- Multichannel pipettes 30 – 300 µL (8 and 12 channels) and compatible filterless tips
- Fridge and freezer (-20°C and -80°C) – cold room at +4°C
- Magnetic stirrer and magnetic bars
- Scales and weighing cups

- A dry water bath or heating block
- USB barcode reader (AZERTY standard)
- Bath sonicator
- Magnetic support (surebeads magnetic rack 16 tube holder, Bio-Rad)
- Wheel with support for 1.5mL tubes

3.2.2. Consumables

- 96-well flat-bottomed plates, Greiner (ref. 655906) with compatible lids
- Reusable reagent reservoirs
- 50mL, 15mL and 5mL tubes with cap (Falcon) and compatible racks
- 1.4mL tubes (micronic) with compatible racks
- Glass bottles of 0.5L, 1L and 2L
- Personal protective equipment (gloves, lab-coat)
- 1.5mL and 2mL microtubes (and compatible storage boxes)
- 1.5mL Eppendorf tubes of “Protein LoBind” quality
- Absorbent paper
- Aluminum foil

3.2.3. Reagents

- Biotinilated anti-human IgG-gamma chain specific antibody (500µg/mL) BD Pharmigen réf. 555785)
- Streptavidin-R-phycoerythrin (SAPE) (Fisher Scientific, S866)
- NaCl (powder)
- NaH₂PO₄ (powder)
- NaHPO₄ (powder)
- Magnetic COOH beads of different colors (one color per antigen), Bio-Rad/Luminex (always keep away from light!) ref. MagPlexTM MC100XX-01
- Antigens (table below)
- Isopropanol (70%)
- NaOH (0.1N)
- Bleach (diluted to 1% active Cl)
- Ethanol 70% (to clean benches) with sprayer
- Monoclonal Antibodies (LA63 (Creative Diagnostics) and KZ52 (Absolute Antibody)
- EDC (chlorhydrate de 1-éthyle-3-(3-diméthylaminopropyle)carbodiimide) (réf. Pierce : 22980)
- Sulfo-NHS (N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide)(réf. Pierce : 24510) (keep away of light! keep at -20°C)
- Amine Coupling Kit, (Bio Rad, 171406001)

3.2.4. Details on antigens used in the assay

Name	Company / Reference	Quantity for size 1 coupling (Final Vol=150µL – 6 plates) (µg)
SARS-CoV-2 NP	Sinobiological 40588-V08B	2
SARS-CoV-2 Spike	Sinobiological 40592-V08B	1
SARS-CoV NP	Sinobiological 40143-V08B	2
SARS-CoV Spike	Sinobiological 40150-V08B	1
MERS-CoV NP	Sinobiological 40068-V08B	2
MERS-CoV Spike	Sinobiological 40069-V08B1	1
HCoV-229E Spike	Sinobiological 40601-V08H	1
HCoV-HKU1 Spike	Sinobiological 40602-V08H	1
HCoV-OC43 Spike S1	Sinobiological 40607-V08B	1
HCoV-NL63 Spike	Sinobiological 40600-V08H	1
HCoV-229E NP	Cusabio CSB-EP322753HIT	2
HCoV-HKU1 NP	Cusabio CSB-EP607323HIW	2
HCoV-OC43 NP	Cusabio CSB-EP333798HIY	2
HCoV-NL63 NP	Cusabio CSB-EP744150HIX	2
Bat 133/2005 N	Cusabio CSB-BP605318BFA	2
Bat 133/2005 Spike	Cusabio CSB-BP610383BFA	1
Bat HKU3 N	Cusabio CSB-BP664686BFD	2
Bat HKU3 Spike	Cusabio CSB-BP663395BFD	1
Bat HKU9 N	Cusabio CSB-BP385259BOV	2
Bat HKU9 Spike	Cusabio CSB-BP385258BOV	1

3.3. Procedure

3.3.1. Preparing the buffers

Note the name and date of preparation of each buffer.

- **Hypertonic PBS: example for 1 L of solution**

NaH₂PO₄= 0,8 g

Na₂HPO₄= 2,5 g

NaCl= 88 g

Qsp 1L d'H₂O sterile reverse osmosis-purified

Store at +4°C.

- **PBS 1X**: Put 1 tablet (tablet) in 500mL of sterile reverse osmosis-purified water
Store at +4°C.

- **Reading Buffer**: PBS 1X + 1% BSA (store at +4°C)
(approximately 200mL per plate)

- **Dilution buffer** (store at +4°C):

50% hypertonic PBS

1% BSA

5% SVF inactivated at 56°C for 30min

0.2% Tween-20

Qsp H₂O sterile reverse osmosis-purified

(Approximately 400mL per plate)

3.3.2. Procedures and Methods

3.3.2.1. Inactivation and storage of samples

The samples to be tested with Luminex must not present any infectious risk. Before any reading, they must be inactivated according to the required health and safety rules, if possible in a BSL3 laboratory.

- If necessary, aliquot under a PSM a sufficient quantity of material. For plasmas, 50µL is generally a volume that allows several Luminex tests to be repeated.

- Inactivate for 30 minutes at 56°C in a dry water bath or 1 hour in an incubator at 56°C

After inactivation, the inactivated aliquots must be stored at -80°C or, failing that, at -20°C.

All precautions will be taken to avoid freezing-defrosting cycles as much as possible.

3.3.2.2. Coupling of antigens to beads

The procedures below allow the creation of a coupling for the production of six plates (i.e. 270 duplicate samples).

Simply adjust the volumes **marked with an asterisk** proportionally for larger couplings

3.3.2.2.1. Materials and equipment specific for coupling

Materials

- Vortex
- Pipettes (P3, P10, P100-P200, P1000) and compatible filterless tips
- Magnetic rack (surebeads magnetic rack 16 tube holder)
- Wheel with support for 1.5mL tubes
- Bath sonicator

Consumables

- 1.5mL Eppendorf tubes of “Protein LoBind” quality

Reagents

- Recombinant proteins
- Magnetic COOH beads of different colors (one color per antigen), Bio-Rad/Luminex (always keep away from light!) ref. MagPlex™ MC100XX-01
- EDC (chlorhydrate de 1-éthyle-3-(3-diméthylaminopropyle)carbodiimide) (réf. Pierce : 22980) (keep away from light ! store at -20°C)
- Sulfo-NHS (N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide)(réf. Pierce : 24510) (keep away from light ! store at -20°C)
- Amine Coupling Kit, Bio Rad

3.3.2.2.1. Manipulations specific to coupling

3.3.2.2.1.1. Activation of beads and coupling

- a. Select the colors to activate; identify the tubes by the name of the recombinant protein to be coupled and the bead number
- b. Vortex the vial of beads for 30 sec, sonicate the vial for 30 sec.
- c. Add **100µl*** of beads into a 1.5mL Eppendorf tube of “Protein LoBind” quality which prevents the beads from sticking to the walls and avoids thus formation of a clear pellet. By default, use a tube provided in the coupling kit but be very careful about the dispersion of the beads and their closure system which is not hermetic (loss of beads during vortexing, evaporation during storage).
- d. Place on the magnetic holder for 1 minute.
- e. Gently remove the supernatant (with a p100);
- f. Add **100µl*** of “bead wash buffer”; Vortex for 30 sec and sonicate for 10 sec; Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute then remove the supernatant.
- g. Re-suspend the pellet in **80µl*** of “bead activation buffer”; Vortex for 30 sec and sonicate for 30 sec.
- h. Prepare immediately (or defrost the aliquots) EDC and S-NHS (protect from light, in aluminum foil or in a drawer);
- i. Keeping the vortex rotating, add **10µl*** of EDC at 50mg/ml, Vortex immediately after, then very quickly add **10µl*** of S-NHS at 50mg/ml.
- j. vortex again immediately.
- k. Vortex vigorously for 30 sec, incubate under agitation (wheel), at room temperature and in the dark (aluminum

foil) for 20 minutes.

- l. After 20 min, add 150µl of PBS (provided in the coupling kit) and Vortex for 10 sec. Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute.
- m. Eliminate the supernatant, add 500µl of PBS from the kit. Vortex for 10 sec, place on the magnetic support for 1 minute.
- n. Gently remove the supernatant and resuspend the beads in **100µl*** of PBS from the kit. Vortex at medium speed for 30 sec and sonicate for 15 sec.
- o. Add the **optimal quantity*** of recombinant proteins (see table in part 3.2.4) to the activated beads from the previous step and vortex 30sec.
- p. Adjust the volume to 400 µl qsp with 1X PBS (from the kit) and vortex 10sec
- q. Incubate for 2 hours at room temperature, under agitation and in the dark.
- r. Place on the magnetic support for 1 min; Gently remove the supernatant with a p1000.
- s. Wash the beads with 500 µl of PBS; Vortex for 10 sec then place on the magnetic support for 1 minute and gently remove the supernatant (p1000). Do not sonicate.

3.3.2.2.1.2. Saturation

- s. Re-suspend the coupled beads (steps above) in 250µl of “**blocking buffer**” (provided in the kit); Vortex at moderate speed (1000 rpm) for 15 sec.
- t. Incubate for 30 min at room temperature, with shaking (wheel) and in the dark.
- u. Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute; Gently remove the supernatant.
- v. Wash the coupled beads with 500 µl of “**Storage buffer**”, Vortex for 10 sec then place on the magnetic support for 2 minutes and gently remove the supernatant.
- w. Re-suspend the coupled beads in 150 µl* of “Storage buffer” from the Kit.

Date and store the coupled beads at +4°C, keep away from light (can be stored for at least 1 year)

3.3.2.2.2. Validation of batch of coupled beads

This validation is essential because it guarantees the effectiveness of the manipulations which will be carried out subsequently.

This validation consists by testing reference samples (usual positive and negative control panel) under the conditions of the test described in this document. The data obtained are compared to reference values obtained with previous batches of coupled beads.

The variation coefficient %CV between values need to be less than 30%.

3.3.2.3. Detection of antibodies assay for human sample

This procedure includes overnight incubation (16 hours) and therefore takes place over two days.

NB - The procedures below describe manual washes. The use of automatic washers (magnetic vacuum washes) is possible and recommended (this reduces bias due to handlers by standardizing washes). Simply adapt the procedures below in the washer program.

3.3.2.3.1. Manipulations of the first day

3.3.2.3.1.1. Sample dilution

Dilutions are carried out in 1.4mL tubes. First of all, you must prepare a rack with as many tubes as there are samples to test. During this step, it is necessary to create the plan of the plate which will remain identical until the end of the manipulation.

For each plate, remember to include positive and negative controls which will cover as much as possible the panels of recombinant proteins used and include also a blank well (buffer only).

Their values will be used for the overall validation of the plates.

***The dilution factor of samples for this assay is 1000. (1 μ l of serum or plasma in 999 μ l of dilution buffer)
The minimal volume of diluted sample needed for the assay is 125 μ l.***

Dilutions can be stored for a maximum of 24 hours at 4°C.

3.3.2.3.1.2. Preparing the bead mix

Antigen-coupled Luminex beads are light sensitive. All manipulations from this stage must be done protected from light (in a dark room for example).

When coupling the antigens to the beads, bead colors were chosen for each antigen. As such, each Antigen/Bead pair must have a different color (bead number (example #18)

The quantity of coupled beads to deposit is 0.25 μ L per well, all in a final volume of 50 μ L per well, which corresponds to approximately 2000 beads per well of each color.

Consider including a margin of error in your mix. For example, for a plate (96 wells) it is appropriate to prepare a mix for 100 wells.

For 100 wells, 25 μ L of each coupled bead will need to be deposited into a final volume of 5000 μ L of dilution buffer.

To prepare the bead mix:

- Vortex the coupled beads for 30 seconds.
- Take the necessary volume from each bead
- Add in the sample dilution buffer
- Vortex everything for 30 seconds.

Wrap the tube with the mix of the coupled beads with aluminum to protect it from light.

To produce several plates simultaneously, handling should be kept to a minimum by creating a common mix (by multiplying the volumes for a plate described above by the number of plates to be produced).

The bead mixture can be stored for a maximum of 2 hours at 4°C, protect from light.

3.3.2.3.1.3. Depositing the beads and diluted samples

First place the plate shaker at 4°C in a cold room or refrigerator).

- Identify a 96-well flat-bottom plate and its lid
- Vortex the mixture of beads for 30 seconds
- Add 50µl of bead mix /well to all wells with a multichannel pipette
- **Place the plate on the magnetic support for 45sec and remove the supernatant by inverting**
- Distribute 100µL/well of diluted samples by homogenizing (aspiration/discharge) with the multichannel pipette.
- Place the plastic cover on the plate and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Place on the shaker at 4°C.
- Set the agitator to 400rpm.
- **Incubate for at least 16 hours (overnight) at 4°C (cold room/refrigerator).**

3.3.2.3.2. Manipulations of the second day

Allow the buffers to be at room temperature.

3.3.2.3.2.1. Washing and adding the anti-IgG conjugate

A biotinylated anti-human IgG-gamma chain specific antibody (500µg/mL) is used at a final concentration of **4µg/mL** (for a final volume of 50µL of conjugate solution/well).

Example for 1 plate: you need 100 wells x 50µL of solution at 4µg/ml = 5 ml of conjugate solution at 4µg/mL final (i.e. 40µL of anti-human IgG at 500µg/mL in 4960µL of dilution buffer)

- Prepare the conjugate solution at 4µg/mL in dilution buffer
- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum foil (place the shaker at room temperature)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 1/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 2/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 3/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, place 50µL/well of the diluted conjugate solution.
- Put the plastic cover on the plate and place the plate on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Reduce the shaker speed to **400 RPM** and incubate for **30 minutes at 37°C**.

3.3.2.3.2. Washing and adding Streptavidin-PE (SAPE)

Streptavidin-PE (1mg/mL) is used at a final concentration of **1 μ g/mL** (for a final volume of 50 μ L of conjugate solution/well).

Example for a plate: you need 100 wells x 50 μ L of solution at 1 μ g/ml = 5 ml of SAPE solution at 1 μ g/mL final (i.e. 5 μ L of Streptavidin-PE at 1mg/mL) in 4995 μ L of dilution buffer)

At the end of the incubation with the anti-IgG conjugate:

- Prepare the final Streptavidin-PE solution at **1 μ g/mL** in dilution buffer
- Cover the diluted Streptavidin-PE tube with aluminum foil to protect it from light.
- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum

- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 1/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 2/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 3/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting

- Outside the support, place 50 μ L/well of the Streptavidin-PE solution at 4 μ g/mL final concentration
- Place the plastic cover on the plate and place it on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Reduce the shaker speed to **400 RPM** and incubate for **10 minutes at room temperature**.

3.3.2.3.2.3. Washing and preparation of plate for Luminex reading

At the end of incubation with Streptavidin-PE:

- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L reading buffer / well (**Wash step 1/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L reading buffer / well (**Wash step 2/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L reading buffer / well (**Wash step 3/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150 μ L reading buffer / well

- Place the plastic cover back on the plate and place it on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.

- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Adjust the reading buffer volume according to the Luminex platform used (the final volume is 100µL for the MagPix and 125µL for the Bioplex200) (*details available in section 3.2.2.3 1.2.2.1 Final Reading Volume depending on the automates*)

The plate can now be read by a Luminex reader (MagPix or Bioplex200).

3.3.2.4. Procedure for using and maintenance Luminex automates

Several Luminex machines can be to read plates: The Bioplex 200 in Low RP1 setting and the MagPix.

Some machines include lasers which require a preheating step (30 min). It will therefore be necessary to turn them on beforehand to be able to read the plates and carry out pre- and post-reading maintenance.

All manipulations and incidents are recorded in a notebook specific to each Luminex automates.

3.3.2.4.1. Use of Bioplex200 / LX100-200

LX100 or Bioplex200 are two designations describing the same automate supplied by different suppliers, Luminex and Bio-Rad respectively). We will subsequently only describe the maintenance conditions of the Bio-Rad Bioplex200.

3.3.2.4.1.1. Materials and Reagents specific to Bioplex200

- Reverse osmosis/distilled water
- Isopropanol 70%
- 0.1N NaOH
- Bleach (2.6° and or 9.6° Cl)
- Calibration kit (30 reactions) – Bio-Rad
- Validation kit (30 reactions) – Bio-Rad
- xMAP Sheath Fluid PLUS, 20L – Luminex

3.3.2.4.1.2. Conditions of use of the Bioplex200

In order to use Bioplex200 in this study, you must read and follow the manufacturer's recommendations. All details on the procedures described below are recorded there (available on the site luminexcorp.com).

The start-up procedure must be carried out each time the Bioplex-200 is switched on.

It is also necessary to periodically adjust the height of the probe.

The control settings must be checked by the complete validation procedure (Optic, Fluidics, Reporter and Classify) at least once a month. If one of the parameters does not fall within the validation window defined by the manufacturer, maintenance should be carried out to correct this. If this persists, contact Luminex support service.

A calibration control must be carried out daily for each use. This can be combined with the device startup procedure. This calibration is carried out each morning before reading the plates. Cleaning between each plate is recommended (Wash between plates).

It is also important to ensure the permanent presence of Sheath Fluid to supply the machine.

At the end of using the device, carry out the shutdown procedure which includes decontamination and eliminates all traces of salts, particularly at the probe level.

Often, an obstruction/contamination of the fluidics is the cause of validation and/or calibration failures. The Unclog and Sanitize procedures can remedy this in addition to a complete cleaning of the sampling probe (with osmosis water and ultrasound). Sanitize should be carried out preventively at least once a week.

3.3.2.4.2. Using the MagPix

3.3.2.4.2.1. Materials and Reagents specific to Intelliflex

- Reverse osmosis/distilled water
- Isopropanol 70%
- 0.1N NaOH
- Bleach (2.6° and or 9.6° Cl)
- Calibration kit (25 reactions) – Luminex
- Performance verification kit (25 reactions) – Luminex
- xMAP Drive Fluid PLUS – Luminex

3.3.2.4.2.2. MagPix Terms of Use

In order to use MagPix in this study, you should read and follow the manufacturer's recommendations. All details on the procedures described below are recorded there (available on the site luminexcorp.com).

It is also necessary to adjust the height of the probe weekly.

The control settings must be checked daily by the complete performance verification procedure (Optic, Fluidics, Reporter and Classify) each time it is used. If one of the parameters does not fall within the validation window defined by the manufacturer, maintenance should be carried out to correct this and if this persists, contact the Luminex support service. This is done in the morning before reading the plates.

Calibration of the MagPix must be carried out weekly.

Cleaning between each plate is recommended (Post Batch Routine).

It is also important to ensure the permanent presence of Drive Fluid to supply the machine.

At the end of using the device, carry out the shutdown procedure which includes decontamination and eliminates all traces of salts, particularly at the probe level.

Often an obstruction/contamination of the fluidics is the cause of validation and/or calibration failures. The Remove Clog and Sanitize procedures can correct this in addition to a complete cleaning of the sampling probe (with reverse osmosis water and ultrasound). Sanitize should be carried out preventively at least once a week.

3.3.2.4.3. Final reading volume depending on the automates

The final volumes to be deposited in the plates differ depending on the machines and are described in the table below:

	MagPix	Bio-Plex 200
Buffer volume for final reading	100µL	125µL
Volume to add after the last agitation during procedure or “preparation for reading”	50µL + 50µL	50µL + 75µL

3.3.2.5. Processing and validation of results – Databases

The export of results after plate varies according to the device:

- Export in Excel format from the result file for the Bioplex200
- Export the results for the MagPix in Xponent format (CSV)

The data used for further analysis are the Net MFI (raw MFI difference and Blank MFI). For Intelliflex, a preparatory step based on the raw MFI is necessary (subtraction of the blank value from the raw MFI)

4. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION – CONDITION TO PERFORM THE ASSAY WITH ANIMAL SAMPLE

Species	Samples Final Dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time	Congugate reference	Congugate final dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time	SAPE final dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time
Human	1/200	4°C	overnight	Biotin Mouse anti-human IgG (BD réf. 555785)	4µg/µl	37°C	30min	1µg/µl	ambient	10min
Bat	1/400	4°C	overnight	Goat anti-Bat IgG Heavy and Light Chain Antibody Biotinylated (Béthyl - A140-1188)	1/10000	37°C	30min	1µg/µl	ambient	10min
Rodent	1/400	4°C	overnight	Biotin goat anti-rat IgG (sigma - B7139) and Biotin goat anti-mouse IgG (JacksonIR -115-065-068)	1/4000 (one mix with the two congugate)	37°C	30min	1µg/µl	ambient	10min

Annex 3. SOP multiplex serology for Lassaviruses

	Multiplex Immunoassay Luminex® Arenaviruses (Lassa virus)
OBJECTIVE	Instructions for carrying out the multiplex serological test using xMAP technology (Luminex®) carried out as part of the BCOMING project
STAFF INVOLVED	Technicians Researchers
DOCUMENTATION REFERENCES	<p>Development of a Sensitive and Specific Serological Assay Based on Luminex Technology for Detection of Antibodies to Zaire Ebola Virus. Ayouba A, Touré A, Butel C, Keita AK, Binetruy F, Sow MS, Foulongne V, Delaporte E, Peeters M. J Clin Microbiol. 2016 Dec 28;55(1):165-176. doi: 10.1128/JCM.01979-16. PMID: 27795350; PMCID: PMC5228227.</p> <p>The xMAP® Cookbook, 5th Edition</p> <p>Bio-Plex Amine Coupling Kit Instruction Manual</p> <p>xMAP MagPix User Manual</p> <p>Bio-Plex® 200 System Hardware Instruction Manual</p>
DEVELOPED BY	Guillaume Thaurignac Signature : Date :
Modified by	
APPROVED BY	Martine Peeters et Ahidjo Ayouba Signature : Date :

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1. DEFINITIONS

Luminex®: generic term designating a luminometer allowing the demonstration of an interaction between ligands (antigen-antibody, primer-target, hormone-receptor, etc.).

BSA : Bovine Serum Albumin

PBS : Phosphate Buffered Saline

SVF : Fetal calf serum

2. PRINCIPLES

Luminex® technology works according to the combined principles of ELISA and flow cytometry through the use of fluorescent beads. The beads each have a different color to identify the antigen to which they have been coupled. It is a biotinylated secondary antibody (directed against human IgG for example) which, associated with streptavidin coupled with phycoerythrin (SAPE) makes it possible to quantify the presence or absence of interaction by an MFI value (Median Fluorescence Intensity).

3. INSTRUCTIONS AND PROCEDURES

3.1. Security Procedures

All biological material must be considered potentially infectious. Therefore, wearing gloves and lab-coat is mandatory during handling.

3.2. Materials and Equipment

The handling of Luminex beads (coupled or not), fluorochromes (PE) and certain coupling reagents are sensitive to light. A dark or light-controlled room is therefore necessary. A source of clean water is necessary whether for the preparation of buffers or for the maintenance of the machines. We have a reverse osmosis unit in our laboratory.

Materials

- A complete xMap system: for example MagPix or Bio-plex 200 (with Kits and consumables)
- Manual magnetic washer compatible for 96-well plates
- Vortex
- Plate shaker (required amplitude 400 - 1200 RPM) (at least 2)
- Racks compatible with tubes used (see below)
- Pipettes (P3, P10, P20, P100, P200 et P1000) and compatible filterless tips
- Multichannel pipettes 30 – 300 µL (8 and 12 channels) and compatible filterless tips
- Fridge and freezer (-20°C and -80°C) – cold room at +4°C
- Magnetic stirrer and magnetic bars
- Scales and weighing cups
- A dry water bath or heating block
- USB barcode reader (AZERTY standard)
- Bath sonicator

- Magnetic support (surebeads magnetic rack 16 tube holder, Bio-Rad)
- Wheel with support for 1.5mL tubes

Consumables

- 96-well flat-bottomed plates, Greiner (ref. 655906) with compatible lids
- Reusable reagent reservoirs
- 50mL, 15mL and 5mL tubes with cap (Falcon) and compatible racks
- 1.4mL tubes (micronic) with compatible racks
- Glass bottles of 0.5L, 1L and 2L
- Personal protective equipment (gloves, lab-coat)
- 1.5mL and 2mL microtubes (and compatible storage boxes)
- 1.5mL Eppendorf tubes of "Protein LoBind" quality
- Absorbent paper
- Aluminum foil

Reagents

- Biotinilated anti-human IgG-gamma chain specific antibody (500µg/mL) BD Pharmigen réf. 555785)
- Streptavidin-R-phycoerythrin (SAPE) (Fisher Scientific, S866)
- NaCl (powder)
- NaH₂PO₄ (powder)
- NaHPO₄ (powder)
- Magnetic COOH beads of different colors (one color per antigen), Bio-Rad/Luminex (always keep away from light!) ref. MagPlexTM MC100XX-01
- Antigens (table below)
- Isopropanol (70%)
- NaOH (0.1N)
- Bleach (diluted to 1% active Cl)
- Ethanol 70% (to clean benches) with sprayer
- Monoclonal Antibodies (LA63 (Creative Diagnostics) and KZ52 (Absolute Antibody)
- EDC (chlorhydrate de 1-éthyle-3-(3-diméthylaminopropyle)carbodiimide) (réf. Pierce : 22980)
- Sulfo-NHS (N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide)(réf. Pierce : 24510) (keep away of light! keep at -20°C)
- Amine Coupling Kit, (Bio Rad, 171406001)

3.2.1. Details on antigens used in the assay

Name	Company / Reference	Quantity for size 1 coupling (Final Vol=150µL – 6 plates) (µg)
Lassa Capsid	interchim A2YIF0	1,6
NP Lassa	cusabio CSB-BP356406LCP	2
Lassa Z	IBT Bioservices 0508-001	0,5

3.3. Procedure

3.3.1. Preparing the buffers

Note the name and date of preparation of each buffer.

- **Hypertonic PBS: example for 1 L of solution**

NaH₂PO₄= 0,8 g

Na₂HPO₄= 2,5 g

NaCl= 88 g

Qsp 1L d'H₂O sterile reverse osmosis-purified

Store at +4°C.

- **PBS 1X**: Put 1 tablet (tablet) in 500mL of sterile reverse osmosis-purified water
Store at +4°C.

- **Reading Buffer**: PBS 1X + 1% BSA (store at +4°C)
(approximately 200mL per plate)

- **Dilution buffer** (store at +4°C):

50% hypertonic PBS

1% BSA

5% SVF inactivated at 56°C for 30min

0.2% Tween-20

Qsp H₂O sterile reverse osmosis-purified

(Approximately 400mL per plate)

3.3.2. Procedures and Methods

3.3.2.1. Inactivation and storage of samples

The samples to be tested with Luminex must not present any infectious risk. Before any reading, they must be inactivated according to the required health and safety rules, if possible in a BSL3 laboratory.

- If necessary, aliquot under a PSM a sufficient quantity of material. For plasmas, 50µL is generally a volume that allows several Luminex tests to be repeated.

- Inactivate for 30 minutes at 56°C in a dry water bath or 1 hour in an incubator at 56°C

After inactivation, the inactivated aliquots must be stored at -80°C or, failing that, at -20°C.

All precautions will be taken to avoid freezing-defrosting cycles as much as possible.

3.3.2.2. Coupling of antigens to beads

The procedures below allow the creation of a coupling for the production of six plates (i.e. 270 duplicate samples). Simply adjust the volumes **marked with an asterisk** proportionally for larger couplings

3.3.2.2.1. Materials and equipment specific for coupling

Materials

- Vortex
- Pipettes (P3, P10, P100-P200, P1000) and compatible filterless tips
- Magnetic rack (surebeads magnetic rack 16 tube holder)
- Wheel with support for 1.5mL tubes
- Bath sonicator

Consumables

- 1.5mL Eppendorf tubes of "Protein LoBind" quality

Reagents

- Recombinant proteins
- Magnetic COOH beads of different colors (one color per antigen), Bio-Rad/Luminex (always keep away from light!) ref. MagPlex™ MC100XX-01
- EDC (chlorhydrate de 1-éthyle-3-(3-diméthylaminopropyle)carbodiimide) (réf. Pierce : 22980) (keep away from light ! store at -20°C)
- Sulfo-NHS (N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide)(réf. Pierce : 24510) (keep away from light ! store at -20°C)
- Amine Coupling Kit, Bio Rad

3.3.2.2.2. Manipulations specific to coupling

3.3.2.2.2.1. Activation of beads and coupling

- a. Select the colors to activate; identify the tubes by the name of the recombinant protein to be coupled and the bead number
- b. Vortex the vial of beads for 30 sec, sonicate the vial for 30 sec.
- c. Add **100µl*** of beads into a 1.5mL Eppendorf tube of "Protein LoBind" quality which prevents the beads from sticking to the walls and avoids thus formation of a clear pellet. By default, use a tube provided in the coupling kit but be very careful about the dispersion of the beads and their closure system which is not hermetic (loss of beads during vortexing, evaporation during storage).
- d. Place on the magnetic holder for 1 minute.
- e. Gently remove the supernatant (with a p100);
- f. Add **100µl*** of "bead wash buffer"; Vortex for 30 sec and sonicate for 10 sec; Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute then remove the supernatant.
- g. Re-suspend the pellet in **80µl*** of "bead activation buffer"; Vortex for 30 sec and sonicate for 30 sec.
- h. Prepare immediately (or defrost the aliquots) EDC and S-NHS (protect from light, in aluminum foil or in a drawer);
- i. Keeping the vortex rotating, add **10µl*** of EDC at 50mg/ml, Vortex immediately after, then very quickly add **10µl*** of S-NHS at 50mg/ml.
- j. vortex again immediately.
- k. Vortex vigorously for 30 sec, incubate under agitation (wheel), at room temperature and in the dark (aluminum foil) for 20 minutes.
- l. After 20 min, add 150µl of PBS (provided in the coupling kit) and Vortex for 10 sec. Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute.
- m. Eliminate the supernatant, add 500µl of PBS from the kit. Vortex for 10 sec, place on the magnetic support for 1 minute.
- n. Gently remove the supernatant and resuspend the beads in **100µl*** of PBS from the kit. Vortex at medium speed for 30 sec and sonicate for 15 sec.
- o. Add the **optimal quantity*** of recombinant proteins (see table in part 3.2.4) to the activated beads from the previous step and vortex 30sec.
- p. Adjust the volume to 400 µl qsp with 1X PBS (from the kit) and vortex 10sec
- q. Incubate for 2 hours at room temperature, under agitation and in the dark.
- r. Place on the magnetic support for 1 min; Gently remove the supernatant with a p1000.
- s. Wash the beads with 500 µl of PBS; Vortex for 10 sec then place on the magnetic support for 1 minute and gently remove the supernatant (p1000). Do not sonicate.

3.3.2.2.2.2. Saturation

- t. Re-suspend the coupled beads (steps above) in 250µl of "**blocking buffer**" (provided in the kit); Vortex at moderate speed (1000 rpm) for 15 sec.
- u. Incubate for 30 min at room temperature, with shaking (wheel) and in the dark.
- v. Place on the magnetic support for 1 minute; Gently remove the supernatant.
- w. Wash the coupled beads with 500 µl of "**Storage buffer**", Vortex for 10 sec then place on the magnetic support for 2 minutes and gently remove the supernatant.
- x. Re-suspend the coupled beads in 150 µl* of "Storage buffer" from the Kit.

Date and store the coupled beads at +4°C, keep away from light (can be stored for at least 1 year)

3.3.2.2.3. Validation of batch of coupled beads

This validation is essential because it guarantees the effectiveness of the manipulations which will be carried out subsequently.

This validation consists by testing reference samples (usual positive and negative control panel) under the conditions of the test described in this document. The data obtained are compared to reference values obtained with previous batches of coupled beads.

The variation coefficient %CV between values need to be less than 30%.

3.3.2.3. Detection of antibodies assay for human sample

This procedure includes overnight incubation (16 hours) and therefore takes place over two days.

NB - The procedures below describe manual washes. The use of automatic washers (magnetic vacuum washes) is possible and recommended (this reduces bias due to handlers by standardizing washes). Simply adapt the procedures below in the washer program.

3.3.2.3.1. Manipulations of the first day

3.3.2.3.1.1. Sample dilution

Dilutions are carried out in 1.4mL tubes. First of all, you must prepare a rack with as many tubes as there are samples to test. During this step, it is necessary to create the plan of the plate which will remain identical until the end of the manipulation.

For each plate, remember to include positive and negative controls which will cover as much as possible the panels of recombinant proteins used and include also a blank well (buffer only).

Their values will be used for the overall validation of the plates.

The dilution factor of samples for this assay is 1000. (1 μ l of serum or plasma in 999 μ l of dilution buffer)

The minimal volume of diluted sample needed for the assay is 125 μ l.

Dilutions can be stored for a maximum of 24 hours at 4°C.

3.3.2.3.1.2. Preparing the bead mix

Antigen-coupled Luminex beads are light sensitive. All manipulations from this stage must be done protected from light (in a dark room for example).

When coupling the antigens to the beads, bead colors were chosen for each antigen. As such, each Antigen/Bead pair must have a different color (bead number (example #18)

The quantity of coupled beads to deposit is 0.25 μL per well, all in a final volume of 50 μL per well, which corresponds to approximately 2000 beads per well of each color.

Consider including a margin of error in your mix. For example, for a plate (96 wells) it is appropriate to prepare a mix for 100 wells.

For 100 wells, 25 μL of each coupled bead will need to be deposited into a final volume of 5000 μL of dilution buffer.

To prepare the bead mix:

- Vortex the coupled beads for 30 seconds.
- Take the necessary volume from each bead
- Add in the sample dilution buffer
- Vortex everything for 30 seconds.

Wrap the tube with the mix of the coupled beads with aluminum to protect it from light.

To produce several plates simultaneously, handling should be kept to a minimum by creating a common mix (by multiplying the volumes for a plate described above by the number of plates to be produced).

The bead mixture can be stored for a maximum of 2 hours at 4°C, protect from light.

3.3.2.3.1.3. Depositing the beads and diluted samples

First place the plate shaker at 4°C in a cold room or refrigerator).

- Identify a 96-well flat-bottom plate and its lid
- Vortex the mixture of beads for 30 seconds
- Add 50 μL of bead mix /well to all wells with a multichannel pipette
- **Place the plate on the magnetic support for 45sec and remove the supernatant by inverting**
- Distribute 100 μL /well of diluted samples by homogenizing (aspiration/discharge) with the multichannel pipette.
- Place the plastic cover on the plate and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Place on the shaker at 4°C.
- Set the agitator to 400rpm.
- **Incubate for at least 16 hours (overnight) at 4°C (cold room/refrigerator).**

3.3.2.3.1.4. Manipulations of the second day

Allow the buffers to be at room temperature.

3.3.2.3.1.5. Washing and adding the anti-IgG conjugate

A biotinylated anti-human IgG-gamma chain specific antibody (500µg/mL) is used at a final concentration of **1µg/mL** (for a final volume of 50µL of conjugate solution/well).

Example for 1 plate: you need 100 wells x 50µL of solution at 1µg/ml = 5 ml of conjugate solution at 1µg/mL final (i.e. 10µL of anti-human IgG at 500µg/mL in 4990µL of dilution buffer)

- Prepare the conjugate solution at 1µg/mL in dilution buffer
- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum foil (place the shaker at room temperature)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 1/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 2/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 3/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, place 50µL/well of the diluted conjugate solution.
- Put the plastic cover on the plate and place the plate on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Reduce the shaker speed to **400 RPM** and incubate for **30 minutes at room temperature**.

3.3.2.3.1.6. Washing and adding Streptavidin-PE (SAPE)

Streptavidin-PE (1mg/mL) is used at a final concentration of **1µg/mL** (for a final volume of 50µL of conjugate solution/well).

Example for a plate: you need 100 wells x 50µL of solution at 1µg/ml = 5 ml of SAPE solution at 1µg/mL final (i.e. 5µL of Streptavidin-PE at 1mg/mL) in 4995µL of dilution buffer)

At the end of the incubation with the anti-IgG conjugate:

- Prepare the final Streptavidin-PE solution at **1µg/mL** in dilution buffer
- Cover the diluted Streptavidin-PE tube with aluminum foil to protect it from light.
- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 1/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 2/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting

- Outside the support, add 150µL dilution buffer / well (**Wash step 3/3**)
- Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting

- Outside the support, place 50µL/well of the Streptavidin-PE solution at 4µg/mL final concentration
- Place the plastic cover on the plate and place it on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Reduce the shaker speed to **400 RPM** and incubate for **10 minutes at room temperature**.

3.3.2.3.1.7. Washing and preparation of plate for Luminex reading

At the end of incubation with Streptavidin-PE:

- Remove the plate from the shaker and remove the aluminum
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 1/3**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 2/3**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well (**Wash step 3/3**)
 - Place the plate on the magnetic support for 2 min and wash by inverting
 - Outside the support, add 150µL reading buffer / well
- Place the plastic cover back on the plate and place it on the shaker and cover it with aluminum foil.
- Holding the plate firmly, set the shaker to 1200 RPM for 1 minute to resuspend the beads.
- Adjust the reading buffer volume according to the Luminex platform used (the final volume is 100µL for the MagPix and 125µL for the Bioplex200) (*details available in section 3.2.2.3 1.2.2.1 Final Reading Volume depending on the automates*)

The plate can now be read by a Luminex reader (MagPix or Bioplex200).

3.3.2.4. Procedure for using and maintenance Luminex automates

Several Luminex machines can be to read plates: The Bioplex 200 in Low RP1 setting and the MagPix.

Some machines include lasers which require a preheating step (30 min). It will therefore be necessary to turn them on beforehand to be able to read the plates and carry out pre- and post-reading maintenance.

All manipulations and incidents are recorded in a notebook specific to each Luminex automates.

3.3.2.4.1. Use of Bioplex200 / LX100-200

LX100 or Bioplex200 are two designations describing the same automate supplied by different suppliers, Luminex and Bio-Rad respectively). We will subsequently only describe the maintenance conditions of the Bio-Rad Bioplex200.

3.3.2.4.1.1. Materials and Reagents specific to Bioplex200

- Reverse osmosis/distilled water
- Isopropanol 70%
- 0.1N NaOH
- Bleach (2.6° and or 9.6° Cl)
- Calibration kit (30 reactions) – Bio-Rad
- Validation kit (30 reactions) – Bio-Rad
- xMAP Sheath Fluid PLUS, 20L – Luminex

3.3.2.4.1.2. Conditions of use of the Bioplex200

In order to use Bioplex200 in this study, you must read and follow the manufacturer's recommendations. All details on the procedures described below are recorded there (available on the site luminexcorp.com).

The start-up procedure must be carried out each time the Bioplex-200 is switched on.

It is also necessary to periodically adjust the height of the probe.

The control settings must be checked by the complete validation procedure (Optic, Fluidics, Reporter and Classify) at least once a month. If one of the parameters does not fall within the validation window defined by the manufacturer, maintenance should be carried out to correct this. If this persists, contact Luminex support service.

A calibration control must be carried out daily for each use. This can be combined with the device startup procedure. This calibration is carried out each morning before reading the plates. Cleaning between each plate is recommended (Wash between plates).

It is also important to ensure the permanent presence of Sheath Fluid to supply the machine.

At the end of using the device, carry out the shutdown procedure which includes decontamination and eliminates all traces of salts, particularly at the probe level.

Often, an obstruction/contamination of the fluidics is the cause of validation and/or calibration failures. The Unclog and Sanitize procedures can remedy this in addition to a complete cleaning of the sampling probe (with osmosis water and ultrasound). Sanitize should be carried out preventively at least once a week.

3.3.2.4.2. Using the MagPix

3.3.2.4.2.1. Materials and Reagents specific to Intelliflex

- Reverse osmosis/distilled water
- Isopropanol 70%
- 0.1N NaOH
- Bleach (2.6° and or 9.6° Cl)

- Calibration kit (25 reactions) – Luminex
- Performance verification kit (25 reactions) – Luminex
- xMAP Drive Fluid PLUS – Luminex

3.3.2.4.2.2. Intelliflex Terms of Use

In order to use MagPix in this study, you should read and follow the manufacturer's recommendations. All details on the procedures described below are recorded there (available on the site luminexcorp.com).

It is also necessary to adjust the height of the probe weekly.

The control settings must be checked daily by the complete performance verification procedure (Optic, Fluidics, Reporter and Classify) each time it is used. If one of the parameters does not fall within the validation window defined by the manufacturer, maintenance should be carried out to correct this and if this persists, contact the Luminex support service. This is done in the morning before reading the plates.

Calibration of the MagPix must be carried out weekly.

Cleaning between each plate is recommended (Post Batch Routine).

It is also important to ensure the permanent presence of Drive Fluid to supply the machine.

At the end of using the device, carry out the shutdown procedure which includes decontamination and eliminates all traces of salts, particularly at the probe level.

Often an obstruction/contamination of the fluidics is the cause of validation and/or calibration failures. The Remove Clog and Sanitize procedures can correct this in addition to a complete cleaning of the sampling probe (with reverse osmosis water and ultrasound). Sanitize should be carried out preventively at least once a week.

3.3.2.4.3. Final reading volume depending on the automates

The final volumes to be deposited in the plates differ depending on the machines and are described in the table below:

	MagPix	Bio-Plex 200
Buffer volume for final reading	100µL	125µL
Volume to add after the last agitation during procedure or "preparation for reading"	50µL + 50µL	50µL + 75µl

3.3.2.5. Processing and validation of results – Databases

The export of results after plate varies according to the device:

- Export in Excel format from the result file for the Bioplex200
- Export the results for the MagPix in Xponent format (CSV)

The data used for further analysis are the Net MFI (raw MFI difference and Blank MFI). For Intelliflex, a preparatory step based on the raw MFI is necessary (subtraction of the blank value from the raw MFI)

4. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION – CONDITION TO PERFORM THE ASSAY WITH ANIMAL SAMPLE

Species	Samples Final Dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time	Congugate reference	Congugate final dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time	SAPE final dilution	Incubation Temperature	Incubation time
Human	1/200	4°C	overnight	Biotin Mouse anti-human IgG (BD réf. 555785)	1µg/µl	ambient	30min	1µg/µl	ambient	10min
Rodent	1/200	4°C	overnight	Biotin goat anti-rat IgG (sigma - B7139) and Biotin goat anti-mouse IgG (JacksonIR -115-065-068)	1/4000 (one mix with the two congugate)	ambient	30min	1µg/µl	ambient	10min

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